

The Role of Human Resource Development on Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

the human resource of any company represents the determinant factor to enhance business development . The continuity of organization and its continued growth and prosperity are assured through human resource development . Human resource development plays a great role in the activity of efficient and effective Performance of the organization through people. The success of any business depends on the quality of its human capital and, while it is recognized that training plays an important role, there are still concerns as to which kinds of training and skills acquisition bring economic success. Satisfaction is an important ingredient for evaluating organization's success. Satisfaction in one's job means increased commitment in the fulfillment of formal requirements; and is deemed as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience, (Locke, 1969). Performance refers to the accomplishment of something or mere working effectiveness. In an organization performance is realized at the levels of organization, process and individuals and the interrelationships among these will define the vantage points of the organization. In contributing to the overall goal of the organization, training and development processes are implemented as this benefits not just the organization but also the individuals making up that organization. For the organization, training and development leads to improve profitability while cultivating more positive attitudes toward profit orientation. The importance of being satisfied with the job is known for more than 50 years.

Key words: Human Resource Development, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance

Introduction

According to Jacobs and Jones (1995), human resource development (HRD) is a continuous process which matches human knowledge and skill with organizational objectives. Charles (2006), argued HRD as the integrated use of training and career development efforts to improve individual and organizational effectiveness. According to Werner and Desimone (2006), HRD practices such as training and development, career development, organizational development and performance appraisal are vital to every organization. Hence, the strategic use of HRD is one of the most important factors for organizational performance. A study by Andersen (2007) stated that learning organizations have become kind of collective term for development strategies that attempt to create consistence between employees' competence and development of institutions. Studies have been conducted in relation to HRD for example, (Ashkezari & Aneen, 2012; Habib, 2012; Saraswathi, 2010 & Sundarajam, 2009) in LDCs. Their findings showed that HRD has been encountered by problems like: lack of training and career development, limited organizational development, lack of effective performance appraisal, lack of employees' motivation and awareness, lack of clear strategies and limited managerial capacity in the public sector.

Performance refers to the accomplishment of something or mere working effectiveness. In an organization performance is realized at the levels of organization, process and individuals and the interrelationships among these will define the vantage points of the organization. In contributing to the overall goal of the organization, training and development processes are implemented as this benefits not just the organization but also the individuals making up that organization. For the organization, training and development leads to improve profitability while cultivating more positive attitudes toward profit orientation. The importance of being satisfied with the job is known for more than 50 years. Job satisfaction is positively related to more complex job related attitudes, such as organizational commitment (Farkas & Tetrick, 1989) and job involvement (Babnik, 2010), which are necessary in present times, where all firms are looking for competitive advantage and especially through their people (Galanou, Georgakopoulos, Sotiropoulos & Dimitris, 2010). In sum HRD practice plays a key role in improving organizational effectiveness. Due to this country developed different strategies to

implement it. However, how well factories in Ethiopia implementing HRD in their organization did not get much attention. Therefore, this study is design to assess the effect of human resource development on employee performance and job satisfaction in BGI brewery factory in Kombolcha.

Statement of the Problem

In today's competitive world, HRD is the fundamental factor for achieving organizational objectives and becoming international discourse (Ashkezari & Aneen, 2012). Based on HRD South Africa (2013), discussion countries should practice a systematic strategy for HRD in support of development. This is because the growing complexity of the workforce accelerated through the dynamic impact of globalization on national economy has just the quest of HRD at the center of public policies and development strategies. Similarly, Livingstone and Raykov (2005) supported that learning and development of employees is the key factor for the expansion of the global economy and innovation in the public sector. According to Kebede and Sambasivam (2013), human knowledge increasingly becomes a crucial factor for competitive success understanding factors that contribute knowledge to workplace environment are essential to every organization. Since, every organization is made up of people developing their skills, motivating them to high level of performance and ensuring that they continue to maintain their commitment is essential to achieving organizational objectives (Abdullah, 2009). However, ineffective practice of HRD can result different problems such as reduced employees' aspiration to learn and apply new skills, decrease employees' productivity, low morale, higher employee turnover and low performance of organizations (Edgar & Geare, 2005). Problems in HRD systems appear when the capacity building practices are failed to accommodate the organizational and employees' needs. Therefore, in improving organizations' and employee's satisfaction is vital through upgrading the skills, knowledge and attitudinal behavior of employees in the organizational setting is vital (Edgar & Geare, 2005). Moreover, other empirical study also conducted by Aliyou (2005), in Amhara, Dessie in public sectors in relation to decentralization of human resource management. However, in this study issues like performance appraisal, how HRD is practiced and critical challenges were not clearly addressed.

The success of any business depends on the quality of its human capital and, while it is recognized that training plays an important role, there are still concerns as to which kinds of training and skills acquisition bring economic success. Satisfaction is an important ingredient for evaluating organization's success. Satisfaction in one's job means increased commitment in the fulfillment of formal requirements; and is deemed as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience, (Locke, 1969). Job satisfaction measures the employees' satisfaction with specified the dimensions of job, such as the work itself, his immediate supervisors, pay, co-workers, and opportunity for promotion (Smith et al. 1965 and Kendall and Hulin, 1969).

Coming to the study areas, no published works are available in relation to the practices and challenges of HRD in factories or service organizations. That is most of the studies in this issue were conducted in public service sectors and governmental organizations. Thus, the existence of such limited researches throughout the country and absence of studies in the study areas which is one of the industry cities Kombolcha, initiate the researcher to raise the issue under consideration. Therefore, this study was tried to fill the existing gaps by assessing effect of human resource development on employee performance and job satisfaction in BGI brewery factory in kombolcha.

Research Questions

- What are the current human resource development practices in factories found in Kombolcha?
- Is there a relation between HRD and job satisfaction at BGI brewery factory in Kombolcha?
- How does the effect of HRD on employees' performance at factories in Kombolcha is rated?

Objective of the Study

- ◆ To assess the current human resource development practices in the study areas

- ◆ To examine the impact of HRD on job satisfaction in BGI brewery factory in Kombolcha
- ◆ To investigate the impact of training on employee performance at factories in BGI brewery factory in Kombolcha

Review of Related Literature

As indicated by Rao (2005), the early part of the century witnessed a concern for improved efficiency through careful design of work. Emphasis of improved efficiency had been shifted to the availability of the managerial focused on the demands. These encompass technical personnel, responses to the new legislation and regulatory framework of the government increased concern for the quality of work. HRD has been growing at a very fast pace in the recent past. Formally it was introduced by Len Nadler in 1969 in American Society for Training and Development Conference (ASTDC). In public sector HRD as a concept it was introduced in 1980s (Rao, 2005). HRD focuses on the developmental aspect of HR with the pragmatic and a flexible approach. Therefore, the intended purposes of HRD efforts are to gain competitive advantage through a superior workforce (Pattanayak, 2005).

According to Singh (2012), HRD implies that the talents and energies of employees in an organization as potential contributors in turn this has a critical role for the creation and realization of the organization's visions and goals. It is also the process of increasing knowledge and capacities of the people in a given organization. According to McLean (2001), HRD is conceptualized as any process or activity either short or over the long term that helps to develop employees' work based knowledge, expertise, productivity, and satisfaction for personal, organizational, community and country at large. Based on Singh (2012), in the national context, HRD is considered as a process by which the people in various groups are helped to get new knowledge continuously and make them self-reliant. HRD is continuous process with a set of systematic and planned tasks in which organizations design to provide its members with opportunity to learn necessary skills to meet short and long term organizational goals (Harris et al., 2006). Bhupendra (2009) also indicated that, HRD as a systematic and planned activity includes training and development, career planning, and performance appraisals for organizational development. Similarly, Harris (2008) described HRD as well organized learning activity to improve organizational performance and personal growth organized by an organization. As Matthews et al. (2000), though the existence of automated activities in the organizations worldwide human resource development is a prominent issue to adapt the real experiences what are going on. Thus, HRD is a subject playing paramount significance at a national level and it is much more of sensitive issue that due attention should be given by both developed and developing countries to attain organizational development through modernizing its employees' skills (Michael, 1995). Furthermore, Deb (2010) stated that it is not sufficient to address people as strategic asset of the organization but to believe that they are the real and the most important asset of any organization and employees with their potential bringing oversize value. Hence, to be survivor in the present scenario of competition, the organizations have to design some appropriate HRD strategies to build their workforce in the organized manner. Finally, Rao (2005) highlighted that HRD as an activity and as a process plays a crucial and noteworthy role in identifying the hidden potential of the workforce employed in the organization is vital.

Components of Human Resource Development Practice

To attain a total all-rounded development HRD is important for matching the individual skill with organizational needs (Jacobs & Jones, 1995). HRD promotes dignity of employment in an organization and provides opportunities for teamwork and personal development need for a career development. Hence, Singh (2012) found that a well-planned system is a central part of HRD in every organization. HRD components which are important for better functioning of a given organization are the following:

Training and development: According to Khan (2012), training involves providing the employees the knowledge and skills needed to a particular current job or task while development is preparing employees for

future work responsibilities, increasing capacities and help them to perform their current job. Hence, a competitive success of an organization is achieved through the skills and potentials of the people that they possess (Leimbach et al., 1998). Training will improve the employees' performance and productivity. Apart from recruiting, selecting, orienting and placing employees in jobs do not ensure success. In most cases, there may be gap between employee knowledge and skill and what the job demands that could be filled through training programs (Abdullah, 2009). Training can be given internally and externally. Internally, could be on-the-job at the work station and off-the job through lecture and demonstration, while externally, by universities and colleges to develop depth expertise (Gomez-Mejia, 2007).

Career Development (CD): Kebede and Smbavasima (2013) argued that no HRD function can be acceptable to the people of any organization, if it fails to provide opportunities for individual employees to have bright career prospects. It is for the purpose of HRD integrating career planning and development with it. Proper career planning also leads to career development. It develops the career of every individual executive, which results in adequate growth of the career of every employee (Abdulahi, 2009). Hence, successful planning is closely linked with career planning and development (Van Dijk, 2004). Upton & Egan (2003), noted that career development focuses on the alignment of individual subjective career aspects and the more objective career aspects of the organization in order to achieve the best fit between individual and organizational needs as well as personal characteristics and career roles.

Organizational development (OD): It focuses on the performance of the organization as a whole (Singh, 2012). According to French and Bell (1999) it is a long-term effort supervised and assisted by top managers, to improve an organization's vision, learning, and problem-solving processes. As outlined by Singh (2012), this can be done through an ongoing, collaborative management of organization culture to enhance the effectiveness of an organization and the wellbeing of the employees.

Performance appraisal (PA): is an important part of HRD, which enables organizations to understand where their employee stand, what is expected from them, what they actually do, where they lack capacity and how they can be updated (Boswell, 2002). PA is a review and an assessment of an employee's performance of assigned duties and responsibilities. PD serves several purposes in the organizations for instance; it provides tools for acknowledging good performance, identifying areas in need of improvement and providing guidelines to justify management decisions (Akuoko & Baffoe, 2012). Therefore, PA is more than simple checklist actions whether activities are performed or not that organizations sought to review their effectiveness and make further management decisions. Therefore, planning, coordination of policy-making, regulation, monitoring and information are also strategically important to the well-functioning of HRD.

Sundararajam (2007) has conducted empirical study on employees' attitude towards training and development in private sector industries. The study came with certain conclusions about employees mind set towards training and development. The researcher found that training and development related programs are essential in the study areas. Moreover, the finding indicated that the employees' motivation to attend in the training programs provided by the management for employees' competence development and organizational development play a paramount role in every organization

The study carried by Ganesh Anjali (2007), concerned with training needs identification in public sector has identified that evaluation of training activity is very important namely in resource deployed and inputs provided. So as to make training conducive, goal oriented, need based, cost effective and duly modified from time to time on the basis of evaluation procedures require critical need identification. Solkhe and Chaudhary (2010) in their study of the relationship and impact of HRD climate on job satisfaction in selected public sector organizations based on the managers (junior and middle level executives) from various departments, revealed that managers in general showed a favorable attitude towards HRD Policies and practices of the organization; satisfied with the developmental policies of the top management as well. Besides, HRD climate has a definite impact on job

satisfaction which in turn leads to the increased organizational performance. Studies conducted by Kumar and Patnaik (2002), about HRD climate and job satisfaction, attitude towards work and role efficacy of teachers reported that better HRD climate and higher role efficacy leads to developing a positive attitude towards work and higher job satisfaction. Similarly, the studies of Forhand and Gilmer, (1988); Litwin and Stringer, (1968), and Srivastava (1984) reported the existence of positive/ significant relationship between organizational climate and job satisfaction; Jain, Singhal and Singh, (1997) also concluded that HRD climate correlate positively with organizational effectiveness and productivity. Rohmetra (1998) concluded job satisfaction is positively associated with HRD Climate; Kumar and Patnaik, (2002) noted the existence of positive relationship between HRD climate, job satisfactory attitude towards work, and role efficiency. Ravi (2009) also in his research of HRD climate and Job satisfaction pinpointed that all the dimensions of HRD climate yield a positive and significant correlation with job satisfaction value.

Methodology

The overall objective of the study was to assess the effect of human resource development on employee performance and job satisfaction in BGI brewery factory in Kombolcha. The researcher had used Descriptive research design. Both primary and secondary source were used in this study. The Primary data were obtained from Employees using **Questionnaires, interview**. Moreover, secondary data was also collected from the documents in the factory, books, articles, journals. The sample size selected for this study was 142 respondents. The sample size was selected using simple random sampling. Following the completion of data collection data processing was conducted. To analyze the data both quantitative and qualitative techniques were employed. The data collected from questionnaire were analyzed through descriptive statistical tools such as percentages and frequencies, mean and standard deviations. While qualitative data obtained through interviews and document analysis were analyzed qualitatively in sentence form.

Data Analysis

The Practice of Human Resource Development

Human resource development practice as a continuous process, which matches organizational needs for human resources and the individuals need for a career development. It enables the individuals to gain their best human potential by attaining a total all-rounded development. It also promotes dignity of employment in an organization and provides opportunities for teamwork and personal development. Hence, a well-planned HRD system must be a central part of human resource management in every organization. This section, presents the practice of human resource development from training and development, career development, organizational development and performance appraisal aspects.

Career planning and development

No HRD function can be acceptable to the people of any organization, if it fails to provide opportunities for individual employees to have bright career prospects. It is for the purpose of HRD integrating career planning and development with it. Proper career planning also leads to career development. It develops the career of every individual executive which results in adequate growth of the career of every employee. Hence, successful planning is closely linked with career planning and development. In this section the study presents HRD practice from career development aspect based on the information obtained from the respondents.

Career development(summery)	Mean	Std. Dev
Working for upgrade employees potential	2.53	0.725
The institution has good career planning and development	2.60	0.719
The organization integrates HRD with organizational objectives	2.34	0.727
Good counseling center that benefits all employees	2.3	0.772

Table 4.3: Statistical review of career development practice

The Table 4.3 above clearly shows that, the majority of the respondents were “disagree” with sub-construct i.e. to improve career development of employees with the scored mean value 2.53. The scored mean value points out that the dissatisfaction of the respondents with the case described and the standard deviation was 0.725. From this fact one can deduce that the factory was not in a position to consider continuous employees professional development to fill the existing gaps. This implies that BGI brewery factory has limitations in critically assess their effort to promote career development by any means to increase the satisfaction level of their employees.

As it is also illustrated in the Table 4.3 above, in the second sub-construct i.e. career planning and development the respondents’ response scored mean value was 2.60. This signifies that the respondents’ agreement response rating scale was “disagree” response rating scale implying that the dissatisfaction of the respondents with the issues described and the standard deviation was 0.719. From this sub-construct one can clearly infer that BGI brewery factory was not in a position to consider career planning and development as utmost importance for the growth of employees in accordance with the education, training, job search and work experience. Employees should trace their career in light of their individual needs and capabilities. From this perspective the implication is unless the sector bureaus are aware of their potentiality and capabilities in career planning and development that could help them to exploit the available opportunities they could not achieve their desired objectives. Human resource development can transform the organization into a human system by developing their commitment and integrating the individual employees with the organization.

With regard to the third sub-construct i.e. the integration HRD with organizational objectives the scored mean value response of the respondents was 2.34 with a standard deviation 0.727. From this analysis it can be deduced that the respondents were “disagree” with integration of HRD with organizational objectives indicating that they are dissatisfied with the case raised out. This result signifies that BGI brewery factory is lagging behind in linking the two things for the betterment of their performance.

As it is vividly indicated in Table 4.3 above, the respondents were asked to scale the Measurement i.e. the existence of good counseling center that benefits all employees. They responded having a scored mean value of 2.3 this shows that the respondents were “disagree” about the career counseling with standard deviation 0.772. This depicts that the respondents were dissatisfied with the case described. Kola chi (2012), in his comprehensive investigation found that employees counseling as the determinant factor to build good HRD. As it is a process of dealing with the emotional problems and issues of the employees to make them feel light and relaxed at work. It can be expressed in terms of appraisal counseling, career counseling and disciplinary counseling. It is also being done to enable the employees to have positive attitude towards work and to improve their performance. However, the factory was reluctant in handling the psychology of the employees and making them happy at work so that they could feel gratified while working which ultimately leads to improved and enriched performance through counseling. It is an indispensable aspect of HRD to analyze the performance of employees which enables the organizations to understand where their people stand, what is expected from them and what they are actually contributing. The purpose of designing the mechanisms of performance appraisal is to portray the actual position of the past and future employees’ performance. To meet this, the targets of performance are set which are being desired to be attained by the organizations. The targets are based on job-related criteria that best determine the success of job.

Employees’ Levels of Job Satisfaction

4.3.1. Employees’ Levels of Job Satisfaction in working condition

Working conditions which refers to the working environment and to the non-pay aspects of an employee’s terms and conditions of employment. It covers such matters as the organization of work and work activities; training, skills and employability; health, safety and well-being; and working time and work-life balance and it give satisfaction to employees.

Working conditions	Mean	Std. Dev.
I am satisfied with the way that that this institutions managed	3.8	0.641
I receive adequate support from my supervisors	4.1	0.77
Problems in the workplace are addressed quickly and adequately	2.4	0.68
There is open communication throughout the workplace	3.9	0.68
I work in a safe and comfortable environment	4.1	0.73

Table 4.6: Employee response on working condition in the sampled factory

As the table 4.6, employees’ level of job satisfaction on working conditions by five statements. The result reveals that mean and slandered deviation of employees’ satisfaction concerning way that that their institutions managed, support from their supervisor , how problems in the workplace are addressed quickly and adequately, regarding open communication throughout the workplace and their filling about safe and comfortable environment found respectively as 3.8, 4.1, 2.4, 3.9 and 4.1. This should that except in problems in the workplace are addressed quickly and adequately employees in the factory were satisfied by their working condition.

3.3.4. The relation between HRD and level of employees’ job satisfaction

Item	Mean	Std. Dev
HRD helps to improve employees’ satisfaction about the working condition	4.4	0.56
HRD helps to improve employees’ satisfaction about the benefits and income from their job	4.2	0.47
HRD helps to create fair promotion and delegation system in your factory	4.33	0.88

Table 4.9: Employee response on the relation between HRD and employees’ job satisfaction

Table 4.9 involves respondents’ decision about the relation between HRD and employees job satisfaction. The mean score of respondents regarding the relation between HRD and satisfaction about the working condition was 4.4 with stranded deviation 0.56. The table was also showed the mean score of respondents found as 4.2 with standard deviations equal to 0.47 regarding the relation between the practice of HRD and employees’ satisfaction about the benefits and income from their job. The last measurement of the relation; i.e, the practice of HRD and fair promotion and delegation system in your factory scored a mean value of 4.33 and stander deviation of 0.88 as listed in table 12 above. In sum, the results of this study revealed that respondents believed that the practice of HRD have related with employees job satisfaction parameters like satisfaction about working condition,

satisfaction about the benefits and income from their job and creation of fair promotion and delegation system in your factory.

4.4.3. The effect of HRD on employees' performance

Item	Mean	Std. Dev
Training helps employees to Produce volume of work that the position requires	4.0	0.12
Training helps employees to go beyond the requirements of the job	3.8	0.22
Training helps employees to convey information and ideas clearly and courteously	3.6	0.11
Training helps employees to do the work with the minimum cost	4.3	0.63
Training helps employees to adjust themselves for the change	4.2	0.63

Table 4.12: Employee response on the effect of HRD on employees' performance

As it can be clearly understood in table 4.12, the average scored mean value of the first construct i.e. the effect of training on the ability of employees to produce volume of work that the position requires was 4.0 with standard deviation of 0.12. This scored display that respondents were agreed about this relation. As the responses of participants in this study showed training contribute employees to go beyond the requirements of the job.(mean score 3.8 and SD=0.22). As it is clearly illustrated in the Table 12, the scored mean value regarding weather training helps employees to convey information and ideas clearly and courteously found to be 3.6. This means employees were agreed about this contribution of training which has its own contribution for employees' performance. Concerning the relation between training and employees efficiency the mean score found as 4.3 with stranded deviation of 0.63. This implied respondents' agreement of good contribution of training to help in efficient utilization of resources. To adjust employees with changing situations employees were agreed about the help of training. In sum based on the response of participants in this study training play a vital role to improve employees performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The findings showed that the employees in the factories had training and development programs; however, they were ineffective in assessing training needs, setting performance objective, in searching aids for internal and external training and development, planning training strategies and preparing training schedules and modules as well as assessing training and development efforts. Especially, post training evaluation was not well conducted to get feedback for their improvement. BGI brewery factory have career development in principle, in order to create motivated workforce, to enhance the capacity of both present and future knowledge and skills, to increase the ability and productivity of employees, increase optimum man task relationship, to prepare employees to take higher assignments and to upgrade skills and prevent obsolescence. However, in practice explicit tasks were not done in relation to the issues described to promote HRD and to attain development goals.

The findings of the study proved that the BGI brewery factory has long-term efforts to improve an organizational development. However, they are lagging behind in solving problems like communication, openness, fairness in treating employees, compensation and job security and problem solving culture. With regard to performance appraisal, attempts have been made to assess the performance and behavior of the

employees. However, the working environment was not conducive as the findings revealed. The reasons for this were lack of incentives and training, lack of human capacity to set targets, lack of objective performance criteria and lack of commitment. Performance appraisal gives equal room for open dialogue but, transparency and continuous follow up was so weak and there is loose attachment between performance and reward due to lack of participation, inconsistent implementation and lack of resources.

Recommendations

Results the study infer that the factory under investigation has clear training and development programs. But the existence of problems with respect to training needs assessment and has limitation in searching external aids and very low external linkage with to build HRD through training which are determining factor for human resource development. Thus, the factory management should plan training based on the need of employees and should search external aids and linkage to build HRD through training.

The findings of the study revealed that the factory management failed to address problems in the workplace quickly and adequately. This may reduce employees' productivity and motivation with problems which are not solved by them. Thus, the factory management has to improve its follow up and support to tackle such problems in time.

The findings of this study implied that employees in the factory believed that HRD influence their satisfaction. Moreover, they assured us that training helps employees to improve productivity. Thus, the factory management should plan practice and manage HRD so as to meet the desired objectives of the factory.

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